

THE IMPORTANCE OF EXERCISES AND TASKS IN THE FORMATION OF LINGUISTIC (PHONETIC) COMPETENCE IN UZBEK LANGUAGE LESSON

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the static and dynamic characteristics of exercises and tasks in learning foreign languages. In particular, their role in consolidating knowledge, applying theory to practice, and developing speech competence is highlighted. The importance of alphabet, pronunciation, and spelling exercises in teaching the Uzbek language as a foreign language and their role in the harmonious formation of phonetic, lexical, and grammatical competencies is shown. It is justified that exercises serve as a bridge that prepares the language learner for real communicative situations.

“It is not an exaggeration or a mistake to say that learning a foreign language is a process of doing exercises,” wrote the methodologist J. Jalolov, referring to the dynamic and static nature of exercises. Indeed, learning a foreign language cannot be imagined without doing exercises: whether they are given in a book (static) or aimed at applying them in a real speech situation (dynamic)!

The important role and significance of exercises/tasks in learning foreign languages as a means of consolidating the learned knowledge, as well as their practical application in speech, can be proven by the following:

Consolidation and automation of knowledge - through exercises and tasks, the student repeats the learned grammatical rules or new words, applies them in practice. This not only consolidates knowledge, but also brings its application in speech to an automatic state. Frequently performed exercises activate knowledge, help to keep them in memory for a long time.

Bridging the gap between understanding and application - even if theoretical knowledge (for example, grammatical rules) has been learned, it is not easy to apply them in practice. Exercises turn this theory into practical activity. The student begins to move from the “I know the rule” stage to the “I can speak correctly” stage.

Developing speech competence - with the help of exercises/tasks, the student gets used to expressing his thoughts clearly, grammatically correct, and meaningfully. This develops language skills such as reading, writing, listening, and speaking. For example, by writing a text based on new words, he can strengthen his vocabulary and written speech at the same time.

Error detection and correction - through exercises, the student sees and corrects his mistakes. This develops self-observation and control. Also, as a result of constant practice, the student becomes confident in his knowledge, becomes more free and active in speech, and his motivation for the language being studied increases.

Exercises/tasks are tools that act as a bridge in learning a foreign language. They prepare the student for a real language environment.

In the formation of linguistic competence, along with exercises/tasks that are common to all foreign languages, there are also special types of exercises/tasks specific to the Uzbek language. For example, exercises on working with syllables are among them. It should be noted that some exercises serve to form only one type of language competence, while others may have an integrative character, that is, in such exercises, phonetic, lexical or grammatical competences are developed in a composite form.

Exercises that form phonetic skills include letter recognition, pronunciation, and spelling proficiency. G. Asilova divides the formation of these skills into stages such as introduction, observation, and correction. The introduction and observation stage is suitable for the elementary level, where mastering the sound system of the Uzbek language is a prerequisite, and this requires a specific system of exercises. The correction stage involves correcting the pronunciation of adult language learners.

Not all written and oral exercises/tasks related to letter recognition (alphabet), sound acquisition, and spelling can be considered relevant for the elementary level. While alphabet exercises are completed at the elementary level, pronunciation and spelling exercises have a spiraling nature up to a higher level.

I. Alphabet (recognizing letters) exercises/tasks:

1. Find the first letters of words.

_o'ri, _elfin, _lak, _avvora, _ilam, _assa, _siriq...

2. Find the missing vowels.

jo'j_, kap_l_k, l_ylak, maym_n, narv_n, _lma ...

3. Find the hidden word using the letters given in random order - anagram.

zumuzro - uzumzor, molin - lemon, maliaz - mazali ...

4. Distinguish lowercase letters by capital letter or vice versa.

A_, _k, G_, T_, _m, N_

6. Find the correct sequence of letters based on the alphabetical order.

A) Dd, Hh, Ff B) Gg, Ii, Ll D) Oo, Bb, Ss

7. Work on different letters (o', g'), letter combinations (sh, ch, ng) or symbols (the stop sign).

When performing alphabet exercises, the words studied within this topic should not be exceeded. They must be previously referred to the learner in the form of pictures or text. Through alphabet exercises, the language learner is prepared for technical reading.

II. Pronunciation exercises/tasks. These are of a dual nature. First, the language learner gets used to pronouncing the sounds of the current language correctly, and secondly, he develops listening comprehension skills in this language. Pronunciation exercises/tasks can include the following:

1. Reading given words, sentences, microtext, poetry, dialogues and rapid sayings.

2. Working on words with different pronunciations but the same spelling (homonyms

and homographs):

tok - tok; tom - tom, yangi - yangi; – atlas – atlas, ...

3. Working on words with similar pronunciation but different spelling (paronyms and homophones). In such exercises, exercises are carried out on similar vowels (i and e, u and o') or consonants (x and h, z and s, d and t, b and p):

khush – hush; rasm – razm, kurt – kurut, kayin – kiyin, ...

4. Repeating the announcer's speech synchronously with a pause.

5. Finding the written expression of the sound – a letter or word based on listening.

6. Work on specific sounds. For example, ng, j (chick, magazine), o', g', h, q.

III. Spelling exercises/tasks. A person learning a foreign language is much more vigilant in the matter of spelling. This alertness cannot be compared to his native language. Because a person feels how a misspelled word or suffix affects the content of a sentence in his native language, that is, he feels that a misspelled word does not mean a rude meaning. However, when learning a foreign language, the imagination in the native language works differently. If a single unit is misspelled, it can seriously affect the content of a sentence or text. Therefore, a language learner always memorizes the words and suffixes of the language being studied, not only semantically, but also grammatically.

Spelling is a skill that is formed with and without rules. If the spelling that applies to the main forms of words is considered irregular spelling, then the spelling that occurs when grammatical forms are added to words is considered regular spelling. In the Uzbek language, regular spelling includes a complex system of spelling of bases and suffixes, rules for transposition, addition, separation, spelling of capital letters, and hyphenation. Spelling exercises are usually not considered independent exercises. They develop in harmony with lexical or grammatical skills. The main exercise/task that forms spelling can be a dictation.

In conclusion, exercises and tasks in learning foreign languages, as the main tool, develop students' linguistic competence. They perform many important tasks, such as consolidating and automating knowledge, transforming theoretical knowledge into practical activities, forming speech competence, analyzing and correcting errors. In this process, the static and dynamic characteristics of the exercises complement each other and prepare the student for real speech situations.

Special exercises and tasks, including exercises on syllables, the alphabet, pronunciation, and spelling, are of great importance in teaching the Uzbek language to foreign students. These exercises form phonetic, lexical and grammatical competencies in a composite way and harmonize them with each other. Exercises and tasks not only consolidate theoretical knowledge, but also develop skills such as translating it into practical speech activity, self-control, and ensuring independence and freedom in speech

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